

A review of explainable machine learning models for sepsis prediction

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Abstract—Studies on sepsis prediction using machine learning are developing rapidly in medical science. However, there are only a few methods whose outcome can be fully explained. This paper provides an overview of selected explainable machine learning methods for predicting sepsis in clinical environments. In order to give an insight into the current state of the art of explainable models, the methods of a LSTM based model (D.Zhang et al.) [8], xMLEPS (N. Nesargari et al.) [9], a Random Forest and Sensitivity Analysis (M. Chen et al.) [10] and the approach of MGP-AttTCN (M. Rosnati et al.) [11] are presented.

Index Terms—Sepsis, sepsis prediction, explainability, machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Sepsis is defined as life-threatening organ dysfunction caused by an impaired host response to an infection, where organ dysfunction is identified as an acute increase in the total SOFA score of two or more due to infection. It is the leading cause of death from infection, especially if not detected and treated in time. Therefore, the earliest possible detection is urgently needed to initiate directly necessary measures. Without appropriate treatment, sepsis can progress to severe sepsis and septic shock, leading to increased mortality. Studies suggest that early prediction of sepsis allows for early treatment and significantly improves patient outcomes. [1] According to the global report of the World Health Organization (WHO) on the epidemiology and burden of sepsis (2020), an estimated 49 million cases of sepsis and 11 million sepsis-related deaths occurred worldwide in 2017, accounting for approximately 20% of all-cause deaths globally. This means strengthening health information systems and ensuring access to rapid diagnostic tools and high-quality care. [2] Common symptoms of sepsis such as fever, chills, increased respiratory rate, low blood pressure as well as increased heart rate are also signs of many other conditions, making the diagnosis of sepsis difficult in the early stages. Clinically, screening tools are used to detect sepsis, including rapid sequential (sepsis-related) Organ Failure Assessment (qSOFA) and Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS). [1] However, these tools were developed to screen for existing symptoms and not to explicitly predict sepsis before its onset. During the last years different machine learning methods for accurate sepsis prediction have been developed for example by M.M. Islam et

al. [3] or F.Guo et al. [4] Deep learning methods perform better than conventional models in this regard. (e.g. H. J. Kam et al.) [5] Thus, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are commonly used network architectures in modeling multivariate time series prediction. However, deep-learning models usually suffer from black-box problems and are therefore often considered untrustworthy in the clinical setting. For this reason, it is essential to develop models that are as explainable as possible in order to be able to use them successfully in the clinical environment.

II. METHOD OF REVIEW

The aim of this literature review is to provide an overview of current explainable methods for predicting sepsis in ICU settings. The research was therefore specifically focused on the following keywords:

- explainable/ interpretable
- sepsis prediction
- early sepsis prediction

Since the aim of the work is to predict the occurrence of sepsis at an early stage and not to predict mortality, titles with the keyword early prediction were also in main emphasis. Here it has to be pointed out that only open-source papers or resources to which students of the FH Kufstein have access were used. Therefore, it is possible that literature that meets the selection criteria was not considered, because there is currently no access to it. Ultimately, four papers were selected that met the selection criteria. The results and models for sepsis prediction will be discussed in more detail in a later chapter.

III. IMPORTANCE OF EXPLAINABILITY

Time series data is widely used in a variety of real-world applications. In clinical environments especially on intensive care units the amount of data generated by multi-modal monitoring is enormous and simultaneously important for clinical and research purposes. Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems can provide an amazing opportunity and is necessary for the further development of clinical knowledge. Decisions made by AI solutions need to be fully understandable to conduct credible research as well as to gain trust and

acceptance by doctors, their patients, and relatives. Elul et al. [6] identified the unmet needs of health professionals. These include lack of explanations in clinically meaningful terms, dealing with unknown medical conditions, and transparency of system boundaries. All these unmet needs highlight the importance of explainability, transparency, and interaction between clinicians and AI systems. Healthcare professionals need to understand how AI algorithms arrive at a decision and how AI algorithms behave in different scenarios by communicating with AI systems through answering questions, analysing cases, illustrating with examples, and visualizing data properties and relationships. Given the in-depth knowledge of healthcare professionals, communication can address specific medical entities and situations through continuous dialogues between human and AI systems. [7]

IV. MODELS FOR SEPSIS PREDICION

The following provides an overview of the models chosen for this review, based on the selection criteria previously mentioned:

- LSTM based model (D.Zhang et al.) [8]
- xMLEPS (N. Nesargari et al.) [9]
- Random Forest and Sensitivity Analysis (M. Chen et al.) [10]
- MGP-AttTCN (M. Rosnati et al.) [11]

A. LSTM-based model

The deep-learning model processes irregular time intervals with time encodings and uses attention mechanisms and global max-pooling techniques to interpret the model's behavior. The Team BuckeyeAI, developed this algorithm for the 2019 PhysioNet DII Challenge and placed second out of 30 teams in early prediction of sepsis occurrence in the emergency department, with an average value of 0.892 for the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC). [8]

Fig. 1. Architecture of the LSTM based-model. [8]

The concatenation of the medical event embedding vectors (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n) and the corresponding time encoding vectors (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n) are inputs to the BiLSTM model, which includes the

output vectors (h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n) are generated. The time encodings are sent to the LSTM along with the event embeddings. They calculate the relative time of each event to the date of the criterion operation and the time interval relative to the last event. Then they use sine and cosine functions of the different time intervals to represent the time encoding for the t -th event. All output vectors are concatenated, then a global max-pooling operation is performed to generate the patient representation vector. Finally, a fully connected layer and the sigmoid function prediction of the probability of sepsis occurrence in the next 4 hours. Due to the shortened distance between the inputs and the outputs, pooling makes it more efficient to the propagation of the gradients. Moreover, the global pooling operation is useful to calculate the contribution rates of the outputs and the corresponding input medical events. [8]

Fig. 2. Interpretability of the LSTM-based model by an example. [8]

Figure 2 shows the interpretability of the model by an example. They display four input events and four corresponding six-dimensional output vectors ($h_1; h_2; h_3; h_4$). Given patient feature vector (h_c) and fully connected parameters (W s; b s), the output risk is computed ($r_i = Wsh_c + b$). The first dimension's contribution risk is 0.42 and the contribution rate is 17.5%, which comes from the third output vector h_3 . Similarly, the second dimension's contribution rate also comes from h_3 . Thus, the contribution rate of the third vector h_3 is computed by summing the two contribution rates. Thus they compute the contribution rate of the input event e_3 as $c_3 = 17:5\%+ 10:4\% = 27:9\%$. For feature j in event i , they compute its contribution rate with attention weight as

$$c_{ij} = c_i * a_j \quad (1)$$

The results show a high prediction performance with an area under receiver operating characteristics curve (AUROC) of 0.892 across all sub populations. [8]

B. xMLEPS

The explainable Machine Learning model for Early Prediction of Sepsis (xMLEPS) consists of a ten-fold cross-validation scheme, where an optimal threshold for prediction risk is sought for each of the 10 LightGBM models. These optimal

thresholds are later used by the corresponding models to refine the predictive power in terms of usefulness scores for predicting labels in each fold. The entire framework is designed using Bayesian optimization and trained with the resulting feature set of 85 features. The LightGBM-based gradient boosting system provides a special processing method for sparse data, which is important for the classification task with the class imbalance problem. For the interpretability of the proposed framework, the LightGBM uses its feature importance attribute to quantify each variable, and the explainability component is addressed by using SHAP summary and dependency diagrams in which the distribution of variable importance is illustrated. The model performs the prediction from the given patient data to determine the risk of sepsis occurring in the next 6 hours. The area under receiver operating characteristics curve (AUROC) amounts 0.859 and an utility score of 0.4214 is achieved. The limitation of this study is that it is limited to only a two-center cohort design from the available training data, which may raise doubts that the trained models may over fit the trained models to each cohort’s data and their patient data. [9]

C. Random Forest and Sensitivity Analysis

M.Chen and A. Hernández propose a model based on a random forest classifier for early prediction of sepsis, followed by an approach to increase the explanatory power of the underlying model. Random Forest (RF) is an ensemble supervised machine learning algorithm, which integrates multiple decision trees and uses the Gini coefficient as a measure of purity to control the growth and division of the trees. Before the formal classification model is build they use a grid search to find the best parameters for the RF. Afterwards several classifiers on distinct subsets of features are trained, in order to explore the predictive ability of the additionally extracted features and find out how newly introduced features influence the performance. For each of the collected feature, the average on how it decreases the Gini impurity, and the mean decrease over all trees in the whole forest is the measure of the variable importance, which can be used to estimate feature impact and select the most significant variables. Then the models are re-trained to gain new models integrating only the most relevant features. For the sensitivity analysis they performed the Morris method [12] on each compact model. They obtained the global sensitivity and interaction factors of every variable. The technique of sensitivity analysis can be applied to multi-parametric mathematical models in order to estimate the relative influence of each model parameter or model input, and their interrelation, on the output of the model. [10]

Figure 3 displays the Performance of the best full model. In (a) the ROC curve with a 0.8465 area under the curve score is shown while (c) describes the confusion matrix of the model. Comparing the results of the proposed sensitivity analysis and the classical RF-based variable importance both methods

Fig. 3. Results of Morris sensitivity analysis to gain more explainability on the RF model [10]

provide complementary information. The model achieves an AUROC of 0.845 and an utility score of 0.427. [10]

D. MGP-AttTCN

This is a joint multitask Gaussian Process and attention-based deep learning model to early predict the occurrence of sepsis. The following Figure 3 provides an overview of the model architecture. The goal of the model is to predict

Fig. 4. Architecture of MGP-AttTCN model [11]

the label for a given set. The Multitask Gaussian Process (MGP) is used to capture feature correlations and for end-to-end training. MGPs are commonly known for their ability to produce coherent function fits to a set of irregular samples by modeling data covariance. They can easily account for uncertainty and do not require homogeneous samples. Starting from a time series with hourly intervals, the MGP layer generates a set of posterior predictions for each feature, which are then fed into a classification model. The attention model consists of two embeddings generated directly from the interpolated data and generated by two temporal convolutional networks (TCNs). This removes a layer of abstraction and thus facilitates interpretability. TCNs are a class of neural networks consisting of causal convolutions stacked into residual blocks. A causal convolution is a 1D convolutional layer that only takes inputs from the past to generate its output, avoiding any information loss from the future. Residual blocks consist of two causal convolutional layers along with ReLU activation functions, dropout, and L2 regularizations. Residual blocks also contain an identity map from the input of the block that is added to the output. Since only up to 12 layers are used, this last step is omitted from the architecture. Since the MGP output is directly multiplied by the weights, the classification model can be interpreted as a scoring mechanism. The positive and negative values are then normalized to represent the probabilities of positive or negative labeling. The model is able to predict

sepsis five hours prior to onset and achieves an AUROC of 0.660.

V. DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows a summary of the considered methods for an explainable sepsis prediction. The models show a variety of different approaches for modeling and gaining interpretability of the models regarding multivariate time series prediction. In order to compare the models it must be taken into account that they were all developed on the basis of different datasets. The LSTM-based model is mainly focused on sepsis-onset prediction for the physionet challenge. There is no indication how this model behaves when applied to other multivariate time-series prediction problems. [8] The xMLEPS approach is able through SHAP illustrations to identify the importance of each feature in improving the prediction of the utility score. This ensures the interpretability of the framework for clinical users. However, as mentioned earlier, this study is limited to a cohort design with two centers from the available training data. This raises doubts that the trained models could be overfitted to each cohort's data and its patient data. [9] Another fact that complicates the comparison of the methods is that they reach different time periods for sepsis prediction. While the xMLEPS predicts sepsis 6 hours before it occurs, the LSTM-based approach is only able to predict sepsis 4 hours prior. The MGP-AttTCN approach, on the other hand, does not include any reference to a time period for which the predictions can be made. If the prediction periods are taken into account, it can be said that the xMLEPS approach represents one of the best approaches. It has the largest forecast period of 6h as well as one of the higher values compared to the other models with an AUROC of 0.859. Eventually it is to be said, that each method is applied successfully to their datasets used, but a successful implementation on other datasets is questionable. Furthermore the different use of features makes a comparison of the models difficult. The models use a range between only 24 features (MGP-AttTCN) [11] and 142 features (RF) [10]. Comparing the results of the feature importance of the different models similarities in the results can be recognized. While xMLEPS and the Random Forest model both have the ICU length-of-stay (ICULOS), the temperature, creatinine and lactate listed under the top 10 features [9] [10], the LSTM and Random Forest model have the heart rate and Mean arterial pressure (mm Hg) in common under their top 10 features. [8] [10] Thus, at least a certain importance of these six variables can be inferred. In the approach of MGP-AttTCN is no reference to feature importance mentioned. [11]

TABLE I
SUMMARY AND RESULTS OF MODELS

Reference	Model	AUROC	utility score	prediction period
D.Zhang et al. [8]	LSTM-based model	0.892	-	4h
N. Nesaragi et al. [9]	xMLEPS	0.859	0.4214	6h
M. Chen et al. [10]	Sensitivity Analysis Random Forest	0.845	0.427	-
M. Rosnati et al. [11]	MGP-AttTCN	0.660	-	5h

VI. CONCLUSION

The review shows that even though there is a number of interesting rule-based machine learning and deep learning models existing for sepsis prediction, there is a lack of machine learning and deep learning models that are really explainable. Machine learning methods have a great potential to support medical decisions scientifically in the future. However, in order to implement these methods successfully, they require unrestricted explainability. For this reason, the explainability of machine learning models developed for clinical environments should always be in the foreground. This area still has a lot of research potential.

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